

Isolation And Screening of Soil Fungi on Different Culture Media

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Abstract:

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to isolate the soil fungi from different localities. For isolation of fungi soil samples was collected from the different fields in pre sterilised zip lock bags. Soil samples were cultured on the different culture media like Potato dextrose agar, Rose Bengal agar, Czapek dox agar and Glucose nitrate agar by serial dilution method. The culture plates were incubated at 30⁰c temperature. Fungi were sub cultured to obtain pure culture after getting pure cultures screening of fungi were done on different media for different parameters and fungi were identified by standard protocol. PDA supported the highest diversity and fastest growth, suggesting medium composition significantly influences fungal isolation and cultivation.

Keywords: Rose Bengal agar, Czapek dox agar, PH.

Introduction:

Soil is a complex habitat for microbial growth and these microbes generally exist as micro-colonies or biofilms on mineral particles, organic matter and roots. The rhizosphere soil sources are the narrow region of soil that is directly influenced by root secretion and associated soil (Stinson *et al.* 2006). Soil fungi contribute to decomposition, nutrient mineralization, biocontrol activity, and plant symbiosis. However, some soil fungi may also be pathogens affecting crops and humans. Fungi constitute a group of microorganisms that are widely distributed in environment especially in soil (Boer *et al.*, 2005). *Isolation and screening of soil fungi* are critical in understanding fungal biodiversity, ecological functions, and potential applications in biotechnology. The great majority of fungal species have at least one part of their lifecycle in soil (Bridge and Spooner, 2001). The occurrence of fungi varies with depth of soil

(Baruah, 1982). Different culture media can influence fungal growth due to variations in nutrient composition. This research compares the efficiency of several media in isolating and screening soil fungi.

Materials and Methods:

Collection of Soil Samples:

The soil samples from four different agricultural fields in Chhatrapati Sambhajanagar (Maharashtra) locality were collected. The soil sample was collected by digging up to 12cm deep and was immediately packed into sterile zip-lock bags. The samples were collected from two spots in each site and were brought to lab for further study. Then the soil sample from four localities were mixed together in order to obtain a representative sample.

Media Preparation:

Isolating soil fungi using Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), Rose Bengal Agar (RBA), and Czapek-Dox Agar (CZA) is a standard mycological procedure. Potato Dextrose Agar is a general-purpose medium widely used for cultivation of fungi. It is commonly used for maintenance and sub-culturing of fungal isolates. Rose Bengal Agar is a selective medium used mainly for isolation and enumeration of soil fungi. Rose Bengal dye restricts rapid fungal

colony growth, preventing overgrowth. Antibiotics such as chloramphenicol are added to suppress bacterial contamination. It is particularly useful for quantitative studies of fungal populations in soil. Czapek-Dox Agar is a chemically defined medium containing sucrose as carbon source and sodium nitrate as nitrogen source. The defined composition makes it suitable for physiological and metabolic studies of fungi.

Different Culture Medium		
Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA)	Rose Bengal Agar (RBA)	Czapek-Dox Agar (CZA)
Potato Infusion -200 gm	Peptone – 5 g	Sucrose – 30 g
Dextrose -20 gm	Dextrose – 10 g	Sodium nitrate – 2 g
Agar-20 gm	KH ₂ PO ₄ – 1 g	K ₂ HPO ₄ – 1 g
Distilled Water	MgSO ₄ – 0.5 g	MgSO ₄ – 0.5 g
	Rose Bengal – 0.033 gm	KCl – 0.5 g
	Agar – 15 gm	FeSO ₄ – 0.01 gm
	Chloramphenicol (added after autoclaving) – 50 mg	Agar – 15 g

Isolation of Fungi from The Soil:

For isolation of fungi, dilution plate technique described by Warcup is used. In 90ml of distilled water 10gm of soil sample were suspended then mix well by using wrist action shaker for 1Hr. at 120 RPM. The flask were shaken thoroughly in order to get uniform distribution of the soil particle. The soil suspensions were diluted in 10 fold increment from 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴, 10⁻⁵. The Volume of 1 mL of soil sample. The suspension from each serial dilution was pipetted onto different melted, cooled culture media supplemented with 1% Streptomycin. The fungal culture was raised by using spread plate technique, 0.1ml of diluted sample was plated in a sterile petri plates, inoculate on all different culture medium. Three replicates were maintained for each sample. Identification of the

organisms was made by microscopic observation. The plates were incubated at 37° C for 48-72 hrs. After incubation colonies were examined under the microscope for ascertaining the identity of fungi with the help of lactophenol staining. The characteristics were compared with the standard description of, 'A manual of Soil Fungi', by Gilman, (1957), 'Industrial Mycology' by Onions et al. (1981)

Result and Discussion:

Various different factors are responsible for the fungal diversity on different culture medium due to different composition. Fungi on PDA displayed diverse morphology (e.g., cottony white, green velvety, dark spores). Colonies on CDA were more limited in texture and sporulation. The present study demonstrates

significant variation in fungal isolation efficiency among the three culture media tested: PDA, RBA, and Czapek Dox Agar. After the comparison done by using various medium isolation efficiency is calculated relative to medium with highest colony count. PDA showed the highest isolation efficiency due to its rich

nutrient content, while RBA provided moderate recovery by restricting rapid overgrowth of fast-growing fungi. Czapek Dox Agar exhibited lower efficiency, likely because its defined nutrient composition selectively supports specific fungal groups.

$$\text{Isolation Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of morphotypes on a medium}}{\text{Highest number of morphotypes}} \times 100$$

Potato Dextrose Agar

Rose Bengal Agar

Czapek Dox Agar

Culture Medium	Mean Colony Count (CFU/g soil)	Number of Morphotypes Observed	Growth Rate	Isolation Efficiency (%)
PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar)	4.5×10^4	8	Fast	100%
RBA (Rose Bengal Agar)	3.2×10^4	7	Moderate	071%
Czapek Dox Agar (CDA)	2.8×10^4	5	Slow to Moderate	62%

PDA exhibited the highest colony-forming units (4.5×10^4 CFU/g) and the greatest number of morphotypes (8). The rich nutrient composition of PDA, particularly its high carbohydrate content from potato infusion and dextrose, supports rapid fungal growth and sporulation. As a general-purpose medium, PDA favours a wide range of saprophytic soil fungi. Therefore, it showed 100% relative isolation efficiency and can be considered the most effective medium for broad fungal isolation. RBA showed moderate isolation efficiency (71%) compared to PDA. The presence of Rose Bengal dye and antibiotics in RBA helps restrict bacterial growth and slow down the spread of fast-growing fungi. This allows better enumeration of colonies without overgrowth. Although total CFU was lower than PDA, RBA provided clearer and more distinct colony morphology, making it suitable for quantitative studies and accurate counting of fungal populations. Czapek Dox Agar recorded the lowest colony count (2.8×10^4 CFU/g) and the least number of morphotypes (5). CDA is a chemically defined medium with sodium nitrate as the sole nitrogen source, which selectively supports fungi capable of utilizing nitrate. This selective property may have restricted the growth of certain soil fungi, resulting in lower isolation efficiency (62%).

Conclusion:

The present study undertaken to comparison with different culture medium with their fungal diversity. Soil fungi can be successfully isolated using serial dilution and plating techniques. Potato Dextrose Agar supports the greatest fungal diversity and growth. Screening on multiple media provides a broader picture of soil fungal populations. PDA shows good nourishment on fungal diversity and provide all require components for fungal growth.

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